

NFDI4Earth

Deliverable D3.2.1

First draft of resource information types (protocols, vocabularies, metadata schemes) in use in NFDI4Earth

Jonas Grieb

2023-06

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8344901](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8344901)

nfdi4earth.de

Citation

Jonas Grieb, Claus Weiland, Ronny Gey, Markus Stocker, Auriol Degbelo, Christin Henzen, Freya Thießen. 2023. *First draft of resource information types (protocols, vocabularies, metadata schemes) in use in NFDI4Earth (NFDI4Earth Deliverable D3.2.1)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8344901>

License

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons "Attribution 4.0 International"](#) license.

Acknowledgement

This work has been funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) through the project NFDI4Earth (DFG project no. 460036893, <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/>) within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI, <https://www.nfdi.de/>).

Executive summary

This deliverable contains a detailed description of protocols and metadata schemes which are relevant for the NFDI4Earth. Protocols provide technological interoperability between Earth System Science (ESS) research data infrastructures, and common metadata schemes and vocabularies add semantic interoperability on top. The goal of this deliverable is on the one hand to provide a compact overview of these resource information types; compact information which afterwards shall be represented in the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub (KH). On the other hand, the deliverable describes how interoperability between the KH itself and ESS infrastructures can be reached by using established protocols for metadata harvesting and ensuring that the metadata schema of the KH is compatible with widely used vocabularies and schemas.

Contributions

Based on CRediT Contributor Roles, see <https://credit.niso.org/>.

JG: Writing – original draft

CW: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing

RG: Writing – original draft

MS: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing

AD: Writing – review & editing

CH: Writing – review & editing

FT: Writing – review & editing

Abbreviations

API - Application Programming Interface

CSW - Catalog Service for the Web

DAP - Data Access Protocol

ESS - Earth system sciences

FTP - File Transfer Protocol

HTTP - Hypertext Transfer Protocol

KH - Knowledge Hub

MSC - Metadata Standards Catalog

NetCDF - Network Common Data Form

OAI-PMH - Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting

OGC - Open Geospatial Consortium

OpeNDAP - Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol

PID - Persistent Identifier

PROV - Provenance

RDA - Research Data Alliance

RDF - Resource Description Framework

RDFS - Resource Description Framework Schema

REST - Representational State Transfer

STAC - Spatiotemporal Asset Catalog

SOS - Sensor Observation Service

TCP - Transmission Control Protocol/ Internet Protocol

WCS - Web Coverage Service

WFS - Web Feature Service

WMS - Web Map Service

XML - Extensible Markup Language

Prefixes

Throughout the document, some expressions in the context of semantic web make use of internationalized resources identifiers (IRI) with prefixes. These are:

Prefix Namespace

dcat <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat/#>

dct <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>

dfgfo <https://github.com/tibonto/dfgfo/>

dtc <http://purl.org/spar/datacite>

foaf <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>

r3d <http://www.re3data.org/schema/3-1>

rdamsc <http://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/thesaurus/>

unesco <http://vocabularies.unesco.org/thesaurus/>

vcard <http://www.w3.org/2006/vcard/ns/#>

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Relevant protocols and metadata schemes for the Knowledge Hub	2
2.1	Protocols	2
2.2	Metadata schemes	8
3	The metadata schema for the Knowledge Hub	16
	Acknowledgements	19
	References	19

1 Introduction

The key objective of measure 3.2 is to assess the technical standards that are in use in the NFDI4Earth. While many well-developed research data infrastructures exist across the Earth System Sciences (ESS), cross-domain and cross-infrastructure interoperability is still a challenge due to the variety of data types, formats and volumes that are dealt with across the sub disciplines (Bernard et al., 2021). The overview of the technical standards can therefore provide guidance on which metadata standards and interfaces to leverage in order to increase interoperability between the ESS infrastructures and the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub (KH). The KH will act as a research knowledge graph for the ESS that collects metadata on research products like datasets, services, vocabularies, articles and more (Degbelo et al., 2023). The aim is to provide a knowledge platform which can be queried in order to find research data or services, find an appropriate repository to submit research data or to find a solution to a general research data management problem. This knowledge graph will be created by minimising manual curation of metadata and making use of automated harvesting of remote metadata as much as possible. The goal of this deliverable is therefore to describe which resource information types (like API protocols, metadata standards) need to be collected in order to make a remote infrastructure (like a research data repository) fully interoperable with the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub.

This report does not claim to provide a complete list of all metadata standards and protocols that are in use the ESS. Rather, the aim is to describe the most important ones which not only need to be listed in the Knowledge Hub on a descriptive level, but which also should be included on a functional level: either by making use of these protocols when harvesting metadata resources from remote infrastructures or by providing compatibility between the metadata standard and the Knowledge Hub's metadata schema. Therefore, the protocols and standards described in this document are generally focused on ESS infrastructures which support metadata harvesting, e.g., data repositories, data aggregators and data services.

These efforts will go in line with further activities, notably the NFDI4Earth label, to advance the FAIRness and interoperability of NFDI4Earth's resources with the aim to enable both humans and machines to locate, process, integrate and determine conditions of use and suitability of data provided the institutions involved. Our vision is – in response to data-hungry analysis approaches like machine-learning on remote sensing data (Reichstein et al., 2019) – to support extensively the self-contained (pre)processing of earth & environmental big data by software-agents or “machines”, foster *machine-actionability* (Jacobsen et al., 2020), increase the visibility of NFDI4Earth's service network and consequent data products, and situate those as essential Earth System Science-related part of an emerging global integrated data space (Wittenburg and Strawn, 2021).

2 Relevant protocols and metadata schemes for the Knowledge Hub

In the following, a general overview will be given of resource information types which need to be collected in the Knowledge Hub in order to create an ecosystem of interoperable services in the ESS.

2.1 Protocols

On a technical level, the foundation of interoperability of infrastructures is the use of standardised protocols. Protocols in computer science mean a set of rules and recommendations for implementing a technical standard (Galloway, 2006). Protocols are structured in a hierarchical way where for example application layer protocols build upon a more general transportation layer protocol, and even more specific protocols (for a particular task like metadata exchange) build upon the application layer protocol. The relevant protocols which are nowadays used for communication between ESS research infrastructures are based on the TCP/IP transportation layer protocol which was first proposed by Cerf and Kahn (1974) and is closely linked to the development of the Internet itself.

Application layer protocols work on top of the transportation layer. The most important application layer protocols in the context of NFDI4Earth are the File Transfer Protocol (FTP) and the Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP/HTTPS) which in broadest terms enable the exchange of data between clients and servers. However, it is not enough to be able exchange data but it is required that machine agents understand what the data is about and what can be done with it. Therefore, certain protocols and interfaces have been established which leverage on HTTP/HTTPS, in close alignment with the development of community metadata standards (which will be described in section 2.2). These protocols and interfaces provide standardised operations to access the data and metadata in an infrastructure on a more fine-grained level of detail, and the most relevant for the NFDI4Earth of these will be explained in the next subsection. Another application layer protocol which leverages on TCP/IP is the Digital Object Identifier Protocol (DOI), which describes the communication and authentication methods used to operate on digital objects through a connection to a digital object repository (Kahn et al., 2018).

2.1.1 (Meta) data exchange protocols and interfaces

In the following, the exchange protocols and interfaces which will be most relevant for integration infrastructures with the Knowledge Hub will be listed. The protocols were selected based on an analysis of which “API Protocols” are supported by a selection of ESS repositories according to their self-description on re3data (see section 2.1.2). This method is being

complemented by expert knowledge, as we added additionally the OGC service specifications and STAC to this list of protocols relevant for the NFDI4Earth, even though they are not included in the re3data analysis. All protocols named in Fig. 1 will be described below, except for the very generic protocols FTP (already mentioned above), REST (“Representational State Transfer”) and SOAP (“Simple Object Access Protocol”).

2.1.1.1 OAI-PMH

The “Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting” (OAI-PMH) is a protocol which was originally implemented in order to facilitate metadata exchange of publications between e-print servers (Open Archives Initiative Organization, 2023). It is nowadays also used to share metadata of research data. Servers with an OAI-PMH interface must provide metadata records in the form of XML documents and, while different metadata schemas can be implemented, output serialised to the Dublin Core schema (see section 2.2) must always be supported. The OAI-PMH specification defines six operations (e.g., *GetRecord*, *ListRecords*) which can be invoked by a client via an HTTP request (Open Archives Initiative Organization, 2015). Research data repositories that implement the OAI-PMH interface are easily harvestable by large-scale aggregators like the OpenAIRE Graph (OpenAIRE, 2022) and will therefore also be easy to integrate into the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub.

2.1.1.2 OPeNDAP / DAP

The “Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol” (OPeNDAP) is a project which develops the *Data Access Protocol* (DAP) and respective client/server software which supports this protocol (NASA, 2021). The protocol specifies interfaces which facilitates structured access to gridded data and dependent variables, thus making it possible to access the specific fraction of a dataset one is interested in instead of having to download the whole dataset (which could be a large binary file). It is widely used for Earth sciences data, especially climate and oceanographic data, where large data volumes are common.

2.1.1.3 NetCDF subset service

The “NetCDF subset service” (NCSS) is not a protocol but a specific service which allows the structured access of gridded data, similar to OPeNDAP (UCAR, 2014). It returns the data per default in the netCDF (Network Common Data Form) binary format, which is widely used especially for climate and earth observation data (UCAR, 2023).

2.1.1.4 OGC service standards

The Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) has released a large number of specifications to standardise the use and exchange of geospatial data (OGC, 2023b). Among these are a set of service specifications which provide a standardised interface for the structured access to geographic information and metadata, which are today widely in use among ESS infrastructures:

- A Web Map Service (WMS) provides access to georeferenced, static tiles (in an image format like PNG, JPEG) of rendered geodata in the form of a map (de La Beaujardiere, 2006).
- A Web Feature Service (WFS) provides an interface to the individual features in a (usually vector-based) geospatial dataset (Vretanos, 2014).
- A Web Coverage Service (WCS) provides an interface to spatiotemporal data which is represented in the form of grids, point clouds or general meshes (Baumann, 2017)
- A Sensor Observation Service (SOS) provides a standardised interface for the exchange of sensor observations and metadata (Bröring et al. 2012).
- A Catalogue Service for the Web (CSW) provides an interface to a metadata catalogue of geospatial data and services (e.g., instances of WMS or WFS services) (Nebert et al., 2016).

Throughout the rest of this document, we will refer to the service specifications listed above, and also to deployed services on the web which support these, as "OGC services". All these OGC services have in common that they define certain operations and parameters (like *GetMap*, *GetFeature*) which a client can use for structured access to the underlying data. The operation which all of the listed services have in common is the *GetCapabilities* operation which can be invoked to retrieve metadata about a service (given that the service's endpoint URL is known), like contact information or the geographical extent the data in the service covers. The NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub can leverage this standardised operation to harvest service metadata and thus increase the findability of the service, given that the metadata fields are correctly filled out by the service providers. In case that the metadata is insufficiently curated, a feedback mechanism can be implemented in order to request the infrastructure providers to update this information accordingly.

Out of all listed OGC services, the CSW specifications is the most important one for the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub: ESS infrastructures which provide such a CSW interface can be harvested easily. The metadata returned from a *GetRecords* or *GetRecordById* operation uses terms from the Dublin Core metadata standard (and can optionally support other standards like the ISO Geographic MetaData schema (GMD)), thus enabling semantic interoperability.

It should be noted that recent work of the OGC includes a set of specifications under the umbrella term "OGC API", which build upon the older standards (like WMS, WFS, etc.) but are designed following a more resource centric approach (OGC, 2023a), thus being more aligned

with modern Web API paradigms like REST. In the future, an increased use of OGC APIs also among ESS infrastructures can be anticipated.

2.1.1.5 STAC

Another specification which supports the exchange of spatiotemporal information and metadata is the "Spatiotemporal Asset Catalog" (STAC) which is compliant with the OGC API - Features specification and aims to support search and discovery of large spatiotemporal data (STAC, 2023). For more information on STAC see the section in the related NFDI4Earth deliverable in Cremer et al. (2023).

2.1.1.6 SPARQL and GeoSPARQL

SPARQL stands for "SPARQL Protocol And RDF Query Language" and is a query language for RDF (Resource Description Framework) databases (triple stores) (W3C SPARQL Working Group, 2013). Infrastructures that provide a SPARQL endpoint to access their (meta) data allow specific and very complex queries. A special feature of SPARQL is the so called "Federated Query", which allows a combined query of RDF data which is distributed among several, independently running triple stores. Infrastructures in the NFDI4Earth with a SPARQL interface can therefore be considered to have a high semantic interoperability with the Knowledge Hub. GeoSPARQL is an extension to the SPARQL language to add a representation of spatial data in RDF/OWL and to allow for spatial computations as part of a query (Perry and Herring, 2012). As the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub will provide a SPARQL interface (Degbelo et al., 2023) it should support GeoSPARQL given its domain of ESS data.

2.1.1.7 SWORD

SWORD (Simple Web-service Offering Repository Deposit) is a communication protocol which enables the information exchange between clients and servers (usually a digital repository) (Lewis et al., 2012). Unlike other protocols (OAI-PMH, OPeNDAP, etc.) it is not focused on (meta) data harvesting, but instead is focused on enabling the structured upload/ deposit of new (meta) data in the respective repository. Due to this focus, SWORD has currently a lower relevance for the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub, where the ongoing work is concentrated on metadata harvesting, but it might become more relevant at a later point in time.

2.1.2 Relation to re3data

[re3data](#) is the "Registry of Research Data Repositories" and as such is an important digital platform for the NFDI4Earth: many (but not all) data repositories which are run within the

consortium are already registered at re3data, and the objective is to register them all there (Bernard et al., 2021). Therefore, with the existing data base, re3data can already serve as an important aggregator of metadata about ESS data repositories to the Knowledge Hub. Within re3data, information about the supported interfaces/ protocols of repositories are collected via the field *APIType* (together with a field for the URL of the API endpoint). Providers state here which type of API their repository offers and can select according to the re3data schemas 2.2, 3.0, 3.1 from a controlled vocabulary which consists of the following keys: "FTP", "NetCDF", "OAI-PMH", "OpenDAP", "REST", "SOAP", "SPARQL", "SWORD" and "other". This metadata information, while helpful as an orientation for a human, is limited for a machine agent which tries to harvest the repositories data via the API based on the information in this field. This is because the controlled vocabulary contains protocols from different levels of specificity: while for repositories which support OAI-PMH it is sufficient to know the URL of the endpoint to be automatically harvested into the Knowledge Hub, more generic protocols like SOAP or REST (which is not even a protocol) require knowledge of the individual API and the semantics in the data it returns in order to integrate them into the Knowledge Hub. From the point of view of NFDI4Earth, this controlled vocabulary should also be extended to include at least the OGC CSW specification, and perhaps further types of OGC services, since many repositories which store geospatial data provide these type of interfaces (adding CSW was proposed to re3data as part of its request for commons on the re3data metadata schema 4.0). Currently some ESS repositories in re3data use the keyword "other" for *APIType* and then provide the URL of an OGC service (CSW or WFS) because the providers did not have a more appropriate option in the controlled vocabulary.

In order to get an overview, a first selection of 147 entries of repositories at re3data which are relevant for the NFDI4Earth was reviewed regarding the information they provide on *APIType*. The result is displayed in Fig. 1 and shows that the most occurring API type is "other" (39 occurrences), followed by "FTP" (which has very limited capabilities in terms of metadata harvesting) and "REST" (which does not provide a standardised harvesting interface). Next comes "NetCDF", which is actually a data format but in this context is most likely referring to a NetCDF Subset Service (or an instance of a THREDDS¹ server, see section 2.1.1.6) - the endpoint URLs provided by the repositories which selected this *APIType* are not uniformly structured and would therefore be more difficult to use for harvesting. Only after this "OAI-PMH" is next in the list with 19 occurrences of repositories which thus can be easily harvested into the Knowledge Hub.

¹ THREDDS (Thematic Real-time Environmental Distributed Data Services) is a server software which allows to provide a dataset via several standardized protocols (e.g., OPeNDAP, OGC WMS, OGC WCS, etc.). A THREDDS server instance provides a structured, XML-based catalog interface which lists available datasets and the different data service endpoints where they can be accessed.

Figure 1: Overview of APIs/ Protocols supported by the initial selection of NFDI4Earth-relevant data repositories as harvested from re3data

2.1.3 Persistent identifiers

An important aspect in the context of research data infrastructures is the usage of persistent identifiers (PIDs). They enable reliable and unambiguous connections between people, places and things and can be classified into PIDs for researchers (e.g., ORCID), for Organization (e.g., ROR IDs) and for research objects and outputs (e.g., Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) or International Geo Sample Numbers (IGSN)). (Meadows et al, 2019).

A good overview in the form of a controlled vocabulary on existing identifiers is given in the DataCite ontology (Shotton et al., 2020). Under the class *dtc:ResourceIdentifierScheme* several individual identifier types are included, however not all of them can also be considered persistent identifiers. re3data also collects the information which type of PIDs a research data repository assigns via the metadata field *r3d:pidSystem*. This includes the values "ARK", "DOI", "hdl", "PURL", "URN", "other", "none". These values, except for "other" and "none", can all be mapped to their corresponding representations in the DataCite ontology. The KH also collects which type of PIDs an infrastructure supports via the property *n4e:assignsIdentifierScheme*, which expects values from the DataCite ontology (they are mapped in the case of harvested metadata from re3data, repositories which use "other" as a value for *r3d:pidSystem* are omitted).

Fig. 2 shows that among the current selection of ESS repositories in the KH, the majority assigns DOIs as PID. However, the evaluation also showed that 81 repositories did not claim to assign or did not assign any of the common PID types defined in the DataCite ontology, and only 66 assign one of the types included in Fig. 2.

Repositories and infrastructures in general, which assign PIDs to their resources are more suited for harvesting the data into the KH in contrast to repositories which do not support this. For example resources which might be uniquely identified via their URL might not be stable in case that the underlying repository software or the base URL of the service changes, which might subsequently produce duplicates in the KH after harvesting.

Figure 2: Overview of PID schemes which are assigned by the initial selection of NFDI4Earth-relevant repositories as harvested from re3data

2.2 Metadata schemes

To facilitate not only technological but also semantic interoperability between infrastructures like research data repositories, different scientific communities developed common metadata standards. The task of the KH is on the one hand to provide information on those standards which are relevant for the NFDI4Earth and for ESS in general, and on the other hand to provide compatibility with the most important ones. While domain-specific metadata standards are especially important as a bridge between infrastructures of the ESS sub-disciplines, cross-domain standards are also listed as they can serve possibly as a bridge towards other NFDIs in the future. The term metadata standard has a broad scope and includes standards which may or may not be technology-agnostic. This means they may have a formal specification in the form of an XSD schema or an RDFS schema but there are also metadata standards without this. A metadata standard may be at the same time a vocabulary, if it consists in a controlled list of terms. We use the term *RDF vocabulary* or *ontology* to refer to those vocabularies which are based on the RDF data model and have a formal specification either based on RDFS or OWL, while only the term *vocabulary* might also include specifications of terms which are not based on RDF. Note that the collection of relevant ontologies for the ESS in the KH has been postponed to 2024. Therefore, this deliverable includes only those ontologies which at the same time are also metadata standards.

For the distinction between cross-domain and domain-specific metadata standards we make use of an existing community resource, the [RDA Metadata Standards Catalog \(MSC\)](#). This is a collaborative collection of metadata standards for research data which provides information and links on each standard and also an API to access this information. Incorporating RDA's MSC is in line with approaches in related community projects, like the F-UJI tool, which makes use of the same source in order to evaluate whether the metadata of a dataset follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data, as one metric to quantify compliance with the FAIR principles (Anusuriya et al., 2020). Metadata standards in the MSC are also tagged with the scientific discipline where they are applicable. The scientific disciplines are collected by making use of a controlled vocabulary: they are concepts from the [UNESCO Thesaurus](#). In order to harvest the metadata standards from the MSC into the KH, a mapping was created (Tab. 1) which maps research subject according to the German Research Society (DFG) classification (which is represented as an ontology as the [DFGFO](#) and which is used as a basic taxonomy for thematic classification of resources in the KH) to the according concepts in the UNESCO thesaurus.

UNESCO Thesaurus term IRI	UNESCO Thesaurus term label	DFGFO term IRI	DFGFO term label
unesco:concept157	Earth Sciences	dfgfo:34	Geosciences
rdamsc:subdomain235	Earth Sciences	dfgfo:34	Geosciences
unesco:concept3269	Cartography	dfgfo:315-02	Geodesy, Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing, Geoinformatics, Cartography
unesco:concept183	Climatology	dfgfo:313	Atmospheric Science, Oceanography and Climate Research
unesco:concept123	Crystallography	dfgfo:316	Mineralogy, Petrology and Geochemistry
unesco:concept172	Geography	dfgfo:317	Geography
unesco:concept159	Geology	dfgfo:314	geology and palaeontology
rdamsc:subdomain250	Hydrology	dfgfo:318	Water research
unesco:concept185	Meteorology	dfgfo:313	Atmospheric Science, Oceanography and Climate Research
unesco:concept175	Oceanography	dfgfo:313	Atmospheric Science, Oceanography and Climate Research
unesco:concept162	Palaeontology	dfgfo:314	geology and palaeontology
unesco:concept11415	Physical Geography	dfgfo:317-01	Physical geography
unesco:concept1557	Remote Sensing	dfgfo:315-02	Geodesy, Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing, Geoinformatics, Cartography

Table 1: Ad-hoc mapping that was created from some of the UNESCO Thesaurus terms, which are used to tag metadata standards at RDA's Metadata Standard Catalog, to (broadly or exactly) matching subjects in the dfgfo vocabulary. This mapping will probably be formalised either based on [SKOS](#) or [SSSOM](#) in the future.

Based on this mapping, the relevant metadata standards are harvested from the MSC by retrieving all those which are thematically tagged to be in one of the sub-disciplines of *Geosciences* (*dfgfo:34*) as in Tab. 1 or which are tagged to be a discipline-independent standard (using *rdamsc:domain0* or *unesco:concept14595*).

In re3data there is also a field *r3d:metadataStandard* allowing repository providers to enter which metadata standard their repository supports. This field requires the use of a controlled vocabulary: a [list of metadata standards](#) that was created by the Digital Curation Center. This list of metadata standards was historically the original source from which MSC as a community curated version developed from (Ball, 2017) so that the entries in re3data can be mapped to metadata standards in the MSC. This is currently being applied during harvesting into the KH, therefore it is possible to show in Fig. 3 which metadata standards are most often supported by the selection of ESS repositories which is currently being included from re3data. As it can be seen the most commonly supported standard is ISO 19115 for geographical data, which even though specific to domains which handle spatial information, within the ESS could also be seen as a cross-subdomain standard that applies to all ESS sub-disciplines. In the figure, ISO 19115 is followed by the DataCite Metadata Schema and Dublin Core, both also widely-applied cross-domain standards, and by DIF which similar to ISO 19115 is a specific standard for spatial information. Only at the sixth rank comes with CF a standard which is more specific to a certain ESS sub-discipline, in this case to the discipline of atmospheric science, oceanography and climate research.

The following two subsections will highlight the most relevant supported metadata standards. As in section 2.1.1, the selection of relevant metadata standards for the Knowledge Hub is based on the analysis of supported standards among ESS repositories according to re3data. This method is being complemented by expert knowledge: we added to the list schema.org, DCAT, PROV, FAIR Digital Object and RO-CRATE, even though these standards were not contained in the re3data analysis. The following list describes all standards listed in Fig. 3, except for FDGC/CSDGM (because the publishers of this standard recommend transitioning to ISO 19915, ISA-TAB (because it is a domain-specific standard to the molecular biology/ genetics domain) and DDI (because it is domain-specific of the social sciences).

2.2.1 Cross-domain standards

2.2.1.1 Dublin Core

Dublin Cores is a domain-agnostic standard which contains a set of 15 core metadata elements. The standard is widely supported and is used, e.g., as the default metadata schema for records retrieved via an OAI-PMH interface (see section 2.1). The core metadata elements were incorporated into an RDFS vocabulary under the namespace <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>.

Documentation: <http://dublincore.org/specifications/>

Figure 3: Overview of metadata schemes which are assigned by the initial selection of NFDI4Earth-relevant repositories as harvested from re3data.

2.2.1.2 DCAT and DCAT application profiles

The Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) is an RDF vocabulary which introduces specific classes to describe data catalogues and their resources on the Web. Its specification uses several terms from Dublin Core and can be seen as a profile of Dublin Core for this specific domain. Open data portals often provide an interface to retrieve dataset metadata in RDF based on DCAT.

Documentation: <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/msc/m12>

Based on DCAT, the DCAT Application profile for data portals in Europe (DCAT-AP) was created. It includes more detailed specifications in order to facilitate cross-portal dataset search. In contrast to the original DCAT vocabulary, which generally adheres to the open-world assumption, DCAT-AP notably introduces constraints in the form of required, recommended and optional properties which may appear in RDF statements. This closed-world approach allows to perform validation whether a certain RDF graph complies with DCAT-AP. More specific extensions of DCAT-AP exist, like the [DCAT-AP-DE](#) (application profile for the exchange of German open governmental data) or [Geo-DCAT-AP](#) for the representation of geographic data.

Since the goal of the Knowledge Hub is (amongst others) to provide structured information on the German research data landscape in the ESS, DCAT and the DCAT application profiles are highly relevant vocabularies for the Knowledge Hub. They provide a detailed set of metadata properties for describing catalogues which contain (research) data and thus a metadata model that can be reused by the Knowledge Hub. Furthermore, open governmental data shall also be integrated into the NFDI4Earth (Bernard et al., 2021) which requires the compatibility between the Knowledge Hub schema and DCAT-AP.

2.2.1.3 schema.org

schema.org is a collaborative project which maintains a broad set of schemas for adding structured markup to web pages. It is adopted on many websites in order to improve integration with search engines like Google and it is an RDF vocabulary (based on RDFS). The broad range of (general) classes, like *schema:Person* or *schema:Article* make schema.org also interesting as lightweight, cross-domain language for scientific data infrastructures. For example, the APIs of the following infrastructures already return per default a schema.org-serialisation of a specific record metadata when requested to return the metadata as linked data: [Pangaea](#), [ORCID](#), [DataCite Commons](#).

Documentation: <https://schema.org/>

2.2.1.4 DataCite Metadata Schema

A metadata schema used when registering a DOI for a dataset in the DataCite Metadata Store. The properties are designed to help in the accurate and consistent identification of data for citation and retrieval purposes. The system is maintained by the DataCite Metadata Working Group in consultation with the DataCite members and under the direction of the DataCite Board of Directors.

Documentation: <http://schema.datacite.org/>

The DataCite Metadata Schema is not an RDF vocabulary. A mapping from the DataCite Metadata Schema v3.3 to RDF has been suggested by Peroni et al. (2016) but a wide use of this is currently not observed. However, mappings from DataCite to other established (RDF) vocabularies, e.g., to [schema.org](#) or to [Dublin core](#) exist. For the Knowledge Hub this means that at least a mapping from the KH-internal metadata schema to DataCite should exist so that the serialisation of resource metadata in KH to the DataCite Metadata Schema can be supported.

2.2.1.5 PROV

The W3C PROV-O is a vocabulary to describe provenance metadata in RDF. In ESS, provenance metadata is utilised to track how data are produced and consumed. At the core, the data model relates three entities: Entity, Agent and Activity. Datasets are of type Entity and they are derived from other Datasets. Datasets are generated by activities at certain time intervals. Activities may be for data processing, analysis, visualisation, quality control, etc. Entities are attributed to agents and activities are associated with agents. Agents may be humans or machines and a machine can act on behalf of a human. For instance, a ML model that classifies an image is a machine agent that acts on behalf of some researcher(s) in an infrastructure.

Provenance-related metadata that is stored in the KH, should make use of the PROV-O vocabulary.

Documentation: <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-overview/>

2.2.1.6 FAIR Digital Objects

Today's data landscape is fragmented, heterogeneous and marked by data silos, underlining the need to build interoperable data spaces to enable true large-scale and open data sharing in accordance with the [European Digital Strategy](#). FAIR Digital Objects (FDO) provide a persistent, robust and clearly arranged approach for making data sustainably accessible and processable by both humans and machines (Machine Actionability (Jacobsen et al, 2020). FDOs leverage on a unified conceptual data model (Fig. 4), which enables interoperability based on layers for PID-based object binding and a typed operation semantics developed within the framework of the FDO Forum (FDOF, <https://www.fairdo.org>) and a community defined resource layer (Wittenburg et al., 2022).

Figure 4: Conceptual FDO model consisting of (i) the PID Layer which enables resolving to a PID record binding all FDO components together, (ii) the FDO model layer that defines the semantics for typed self-contained processing of an FDO's data (Machine Actionability) and (iii) the Resource layer comprising encapsulated operations, metadata as well as policies either included as payload or linked as references.

2.2.1.7 RO-CRATE

RO-Crate is a data model for lightweight containers packaging primary research data with their metadata based on adaptable metadata profiles (Sefton et al., 2023). Leveraging on web technologies including the JSON-LD format and the schema.org vocabulary, RO-Crate can realise FAIR Digital Objects combining PIDs and [FAIR Signposting](#). RO-Crates are successfully

employed to package data cubes of earth observation data (Fouilloux et al., 2022) and are therefore a technology candidate to implement FDOs for the KH.

Documentation: <https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.1>

2.2.1.8 OAI-ORE

OAI-ORE (Open Archives Initiative Object Reuse and Exchange) is a standard for the description and exchange of distributed Web resources which are aggregations of text and other media types. It makes use of semantic web standards (URIs, metadata in RDF), e.g., by making the use of some Dublin Core Terms elements mandatory in the metadata. Given that OAI-ORE is only supported by one repository in Fig. 3, and that the specification has not received many updates since the first release in 2008, it can be assumed that OAI-ORE is not widely used anymore, and will probably be replaced by newer standards, like RO-CRATE.

Documentation: <http://www.openarchives.org/ore/>

2.2.2 Domain-specific standards

2.2.2.1 ISO 19115

ISO 19115 is an internationally recognised scheme for describing geographic information and services. It describes the metadata for the identification, scope, quality, spatial and temporal extent, spatial reference and distribution of digital geodata.

ISO 19115-1:2014 provides the basics of the standard; ISO 19115-2:2009 provides extensions for image and grid data; and ISO/TS 19115-3:2016 provides an XML Schema implementation for ISO/TS 19138:2007 compatible concepts such as Geographic Metadata XML, or GMD.

Documentation: <https://standards.iso.org/iso/19115/-3/>

2.2.2.2 CF (Climate and Forecast)

The Climate and Forecast Metadata Conventions were originally designed to ensure that datasets in netCDF format provide complete metadata on the variables that are described in the dataset. However the standard itself is not limited to netCDF data. It is intended for use for climate and forecast data and thus can be seen as a domain-specific metadata standard for the atmospheric sciences, oceanography and climate research (*dfgfo:313* in terms of the German Research Society's subject classification). Fig. 3 shows that it is the sixth most often supported metadata standard in the selection of German ESS repositories and therefore the most commonly supported domain-specific metadata standard.

Documentation: <http://cfconventions.org/>

2.2.2.3 Darwin Core, ABCD and EML

Darwin Core, ABCD (*Access to Biological Collection Data*) and EML (*Ecological Metadata Language*) are three partially overlapping standards for mobilisation, documentation and sharing of biodiversity data. They provide information elements to describe the taxonomic, spatio-temporal and thematic content of datasets in the domain of geo- and biodiversity. All of them are closely linked to the data mobilisation for aggregators like GBIF and GeoCAsE. ABCD-EFG (Access to Biological Collection Databases Extended for Geosciences) is an extension to ABCD for use with palaeontological, mineralogical and geological digitalised collection data.

2.2.2.4 CIF (Crystallographic Information Framework)

CIF is a standard file structure for distributing crystallographic data. If considering crystallography as broadly being related to the research subject area of mineralogy, petrology and geochemistry (dfgo:316), then according to Fig. 3 it is the only metadata standard from this specific research discipline that is currently marked as supported in re3data by at least one German ESS infrastructure. This is probably a lack in documentation rather than in missing metadata standards for this research discipline which should be tackled in the course of the further development of the Knowledge Hub and related products in the NFDI4Earth.

Documentation: <https://www.iucr.org/resources/cif/spec>

2.2.2.5 DIF (Directory Interchange Format)

DIF is a metadata interchange format for ESS data on a collection level (not for individual records). It is defined in the form of an XML Schema (NASA, 2023). Its roots date back to the 1980s, but it remains an actively maintained standard, with having its last updated release in 2019 and still being supported by various of the selected re3data repositories (Fig. 3). However, as stated by NASA, some metadata providers are in favour of superseding DIF with the newer ISO 19915 standard. Therefore, providing interoperability with DIF should have a lower priority than interoperability with ISO 19915 for the Knowledge Hub.

Documentation: https://idn.ceos.org/Aboutus/xml/dif/dif_v10.2.xsd

2.2.3 Other vocabularies

As was mentioned above, a more complete list of relevant RDF vocabularies and ontologies for the ESS will be collected in upcoming iterations of further development of the Knowledge Hub. However, this section lists other vocabularies which are important for the Knowledge Hub on a functional level.

GeoNames

[GeoNames](#) is an online database of geographical names with worldwide coverage, published under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License. Each place receives a unique identifier which at the same time is a resolvable IRI. Via a semantic web API, data about individual places can be retrieved in RDF, based on the [GeoNames ontology](#). Other important public datasets make use of GeoNames, for example, the Research Organization Registry (ROR) only curates the GeoNames ID of the city where an organisation is located, and further relevant information (like the latitude and longitude coordinates of the city center, and the administrative area) is retrieved from GeoNames. The Knowledge Hub, given the spatial dimension of many of its metadata elements, should therefore also make use of GeoNames wherever unique identifiers of geographic locations are stored.

3 The metadata schema for the Knowledge Hub

The resource information types presented in the previous section will be represented in the Knowledge Hub. The Knowledge Hub as a knowledge graph stores semantically annotated metadata resources in RDF and can be queried via a SPARQL interface (Degbelo et al., 2023). A variety of serialisation formats for RDF exist, like Turtle, RDF/XML, JSON-LD, which all comply with the RDF data model and therefore enable a lossless conversion from one format to the other. In contrast to many other systems, which store their data for example in a relational database and only then provide a serialisation option to RDF to their clients, the goal of the Knowledge Hub is store all its metadata natively as linked data, that is, in an RDF format. In order to provide a high interoperability and to reduce mapping efforts, the metadata in the Knowledge Hub should make use of established RDF vocabularies as much as possible. Many harvestable infrastructures already provide the option to serialise their data into an RDF format, however to make the most out of queries to the Knowledge Hub it is also necessary that its metadata follows a unified schema and to define closed-world validation rules which ensure that a resource's metadata meets some minimal requirements in order to be included in the KH. In the following the current status of this schema will be described.

The metadata schema of the KH implements two major cross-domain vocabularies, DCAT and schema.org. schema.org was chosen because of its wide spread use and broad range of classes which cover many general resource types (like *Article*, *SoftwareSourceCode*, ...). It also provides a class for *Dataset*, however for all resource types which cover the domain of data catalogues (*Dataset*, *Distribution*, *Catalog*, *DataService*, ...) the respective classes of the DCAT vocabulary were chosen which allow a more specific description of this domain. Furthermore, this increases the interoperability between the KH and governmental resources which rely on the DCAT-AP standard to register governmental open data in nationwide (govdata.de) or EU-wide (data.europa.eu) aggregated catalogues.

DCAT offers a class *Catalog* which is suited to describe many infrastructures which are run within

the NFDI4Earth: (digital) platforms which allow for the search and download of research data. However, the *Catalog* class is lacking specific properties which are required in the Knowledge Hub especially with respect to the description of data submission. Therefore, we define three more specific subclasses of *dcat:Catalog* in the NFDI4Earth namespace:

1. *n4e:Repository*: A research data repository which stores research data and makes it available (usually in the form of a web-based catalogue). It allows the submission of data at least from within the institution where it is run (institutional repository) and might also be available for external data submission.
2. *n4e:Aggregator*: A catalogue which provides a structured metadata search. It does not host any primary data by itself, instead it harvests the metadata from remote resources and provides them in an aggregated (and optionally processed) way.
3. *n4e:Registry*: A catalogue which registers metadata and thus provides (persistent) identifiers for remote resources. Examples are the Research Organization Registry (ROR), re3data, or the RDA's Metadata Standard Catalog (MSC).

The property *n4e:supportsMetadataStandard* is defined and used to link a catalogue to the metadata standard (as listed in section 2.2) it supports, where the metadata standard itself must be a resource listed in the KH (class *n4e:MetadataStandard*). The property *n4e:assignsIdentifierScheme* is used to link a catalogue to the PID type that is assigned to resources in the catalogue. The property *dcat:distribution* links a dataset to a downloadable representation (class *dcat:Distribution*), but used on catalogues we use it to describe the API interface that the catalogue provides.

Linked to these classes we collect metadata on organisations (using *foaf:Organization* as recommended by the DCAT vocabulary), datasets (*dcat:Dataset*) and data services (*dcat:DataService*) in the Knowledge Hub. Data services are collected in the form of OGC service endpoints and NetCDF subset services provided by infrastructures within the consortium, but this can also be extended with further standardised exchange protocols (see section 2.1) in the future. Spatial information, e.g., the spatial coverage of a catalogue or a dataset or the location where an organisation is based is described with terms from the GeoSPARQL specification (<http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql>) for geometries, and with GeoNames identifiers, respectively. Datasets are not yet harvested by the Knowledge Hub at the time of writing, however by indexing the existing repositories and catalogues, together with the interfaces and metadata standards they support, the ground work is being laid to implement a structured, large-scale harvesting setup of dataset metadata in the next iteration of Knowledge Hub development.

Fig. 5 gives a simplified overview on the currently included classes in the Knowledge Hub Metadata scheme, and their hierarchy. This is only a snapshot of the current state, the Knowledge Hub Metadata scheme will evolve over the time. Furthermore it has to be noted, that this current state is still a work in progress and a first release is expected to be made

CREATED WITH YUML

Figure 5: Overview of the class hierarchy of the current Knowledge Hub schema. Note that the parent classes *Thing*, *CreativeWork* and *Resource* are not supposed to be instantiated in the Knowledge Hub, only their respective subclasses are resource information types of interest.

together with the release of the first version of the KH itself. The description of the scheme in this section is only rough summary, a more detailed, interactive documentation of the KH schema is currently hosted at: <https://nfdi4earth.pages.rwth-aachen.de/knowledgehub/nfdi4earth-kh-schema/>

Acknowledgements

We thank members of the NFDI4Earth Data Model Expert Group and the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub Working Group for their contributions in shaping these ideas (in alphabetical order): Ivonne Anders, Stephan Hachinger, Sibylle Haßler, Frank Kratzenstein, Ralf Klammer, Johannes Munke, Claudia Müller, Christopher Purr, Valentina Protopopova, Thomas Rose, Farzaneh Sadeghi, Freya Thießen, Peter Valena, Alexander Wellmann.

References

- Devaraju, Anusuriya, *et al.* (2020) FAIRsFAIR data object assessment metrics. Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213>.
- Ball, A. (2017) 'Metadata Standards Directory'. Available at: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/metadata-standards-directory> (Accessed: 20 June 2023).
- Baumann, P. (2017) 'OGC Web Coverage Service (WCS) 2.1 Interface Standard—Core. 2018'. Open Geospatial Consortium. Available at: <http://www.opengis.net/doc/IS/wcs-core/2.1> (Accessed: 19 June 2023).
- Bernard, L. *et al.* (2021) 'NFDI Consortium Earth System Sciences - Proposal 2020 revised'. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5718944>.
- Bröring, A., Stasch, C. and Echterhoff, J. (eds) (2012) 'OGC Sensor Observation Service Interface Standard, Version 2.0'. Open Geospatial Consortium. <https://doi.org/10.25607/OBP-452>.
- Cerf, V. and Kahn, R. (1974) 'A Protocol for Packet Network Intercommunication', *IEEE Transactions on Communications*. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE), 22(5), pp. 637–648. doi: 10.1109/tcom.1974.1092259.
- Cremer, F. *et al.* (2023) 'Overview of data cube technologies and review of other emerging technologies (NFDI4Earth Deliverable D2.5.1)'. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7951050>.
- Degbelo, A. *et al.* (2023) 'NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub - Concept (NFDI4Earth Deliverable D4.3.2)'. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7950860>.

Fouilloux, A., Foglini, F. and Trasatti, E. (2022) 'FAIR Research Objects for realizing Open Science with RELIANCE EOSC project', *Research Ideas and Outcomes*. Pensoft Publishers, 8. doi: 10.3897/rio.8.e93940.

Galloway, A. R. (2006) 'Protocol', *Theory, Culture and Society*. SAGE Publications, 23(2-3), pp. 317-320. <https://doi.org/10.1177/026327640602300241>.

Jacobsen, A. *et al.* (2020) 'FAIR Principles: Interpretations and Implementation Considerations', *Data Intelligence*. MIT Press - Journals, 2(1-2), pp. 10-29. https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_r_00024.

Kahn, R. E. *et al.* (2018) 'Digital Object Interface Protocol Specification Version 2.0'. Available at: https://www.dona.net/sites/default/files/2018-11/DOIPv2Spec_1.pdf (Accessed: 23 June 2023).

de La Beaujardiere, J. (2006) 'OpenGIS® Web Map Server Implementation Specification. Version 1.3.0'. Open Geospatial Consortium. Available at: https://portal.ogc.org/files/?artifact_id=14416 (Accessed: 19 June 2023).

Lagoze, C. *et al.* (2002) 'Open archives initiative-protocol for metadata harvesting-v. 2.0'. Available at: <https://www.openarchives.org/OAI/openarchivesprotocol.html> (Accessed: 20 June 2023).

Lewis, S. *et al.* (2012). SWORD: Facilitating deposit scenarios. *D-Lib Magazine*, 18(1/2). <https://doi.org/10.1045/january2012-lewis>.

Meadows, A., Haak, L. L. and Brown, J. (2019) 'Persistent identifiers: the building blocks of the research information infrastructure', *Insights the UKSG journal*. Ubiquity Press, Ltd., 32. doi: 10.1629/uksg.457.

Nasa (2023) Directory Interchange Format (DIF) Standard. Available at: <https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/esdis/esco/standards-and-practices/directory-interchange-format-dif-standard> (Accessed 14 August 2023).

Nasa (2021) 'What is OPeNDAP?' Available at: <https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/engage/open-data-services-and-software/api/opendap> (Accessed: 20 June 2023).

Nebert, D., Voges, U. and Bigagli, L. (eds) (2016) 'OGC® Catalogue Services 3.0 - General Model, Version 3.0'. Open Geospatial Consortium. <https://doi.org/10.25607/OBP-591>.

OGC - Open Geospatial Consortium (2023b) 'Standards'. Available at: <https://www.ogc.org/standards/> (Accessed: 20 June 2023).

OGC - Open Geospatial Consortium (2023a) 'OGC APIs - Building Blocks for Location'. Available at: <https://ogcapi.ogc.org/> (Accessed: 20 June 2023).

Open Archives Initiative Organization (no date) 'About OAI'. Available at: <https://www.openarchives.org/organization/> (Accessed: 19 June 2023).

OpenAIRE (2022) 'Use of OAI-PMH'. Available at: https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/literature/use_of_oai_pmh.html (Accessed: 19 June 2023).

Peroni, S. *et al.* (2016) 'DataCite2RDF: Mapping DataCite Metadata Schema 3.1 Terms to RDF'. figshare. <https://doi.org/10.6084/M9.FIGSHARE.2075356.V1>.

Perry, M. and Herring, J. (eds) (2012) 'OGC GeoSPARQL - A Geographic Query Language for RDF Data'. Open Geospatial Consortium. Available at: <http://www.opengis.net/doc/IS/geosparql/1.0> (Accessed: 20 June 2023).

Reichstein, M. *et al.* (2019) 'Deep learning and process understanding for data-driven Earth system science', *Nature*. Nature Publishing Group UK London, 566(7743), pp. 195–204. Available at: https://pure.mpg.de/rest/items/item_3029184_5/component/file_3282959/content (Accessed: 20 June 2023).

Stac (2023) 'About STAC - Frequently Asked Questions'. Available at: <https://stacspec.org/en/about/frequently-asked-questions/> (Accessed: 20 June 2023).

Sefton, P. *et al.* (2023) 'RO-Crate Metadata Specification 1.1.3'. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3406497>.

Shotton, D. *et al.* (2020) 'The DataCite Ontology'. Available at: <http://purl.org/spar/datacite> (Accessed: 20 June 2023).

UCAR - University Corporation for Atmospheric Research (2014) 'NetCDF Subset Service Reference'. Available at: <https://docs.unidata.ucar.edu/tds/4.6/adminguide/reference/NetcdfSubsetServiceReference.html> (Accessed: 20 June 2023).

UCAR - University Corporation for Atmospheric Research (2023) 'Where is NetCDF Used?' Available at: <https://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/usage.html> (Accessed: 20 June 2023).

Vretanos, P. P. A. (2014) 'OGC® Web Feature Service 2.0 Interface Standard--With Corrigendum, Version 2.0. 2'. Open Geospatial Consortium. Available at: <http://www.opengis.net/doc/IS/wfs/2.0.2> (Accessed: 19 June 2023).

W3C SPARQL Working Group (2013) 'SPARQL 1.1 overview'. World Wide Web Consortium. Available at: <https://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-overview/> (Accessed: 20 June 2023).

Wittenburg, P. and Strawn, G. (2021) 'Revolutions Take Time', *Information*. MDPI AG, 12(11), p. 472. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info12110472>.

Wittenburg, P. *et al.* (2022) 'FAIR Digital Object Demonstrators 2021'. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5872645>.